

Appendix 5. List of Additional Materials

The English version of this report took just over two years to prepare (mid-2018 to mid-2020). Our intention is to make the existing (and future) materials to be as accessible as possible. This appendix provides an overview of the available materials for this report.

5.1. Versions of this report

The German version of (late) 2019 is available here:

Haßler, B., et al., (2019). *Berufsbildung in Sub-Sahara Afrika: Stand der Forschung*. VET Repository, Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung, Bonn, Germany. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3334690](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3334690). Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/GEELRK57>.

The English version (July 2020) is available here:

Haßler, B., Haseloff, G., et al. (2020). *Technical and Vocational Education and Training in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review of the Research Landscape (1st ed.)*. VET Repository, Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung, Bonn, Germany. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3572897](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3572897). Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/ZEDIHF57>.

We have also allocated a DOI for a potentially forthcoming 2nd edition:

Forthcoming: *Technical and Vocational Education and Training in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review of the Research Landscape (2nd ed.)*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3970782](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3970782). Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/EHKG4JUL>.

5.2. Chapters in this report

The chapters in this report have their own DOIs assigned, to make it easier to quote and reuse them.

Chapter number	Chapter name	DOI	Citation and references
	Executive Summary	10.5281/zenodo.3843340	↑link
1	Introduction	10.5281/zenodo.3843342	↑link
2	Research Design	10.5281/zenodo.3843344	↑link
3	Overview of the dDiscovered Publications	10.5281/zenodo.3843346	↑link
4	The Conception and pPractice of TVET in SSA	10.5281/zenodo.3843348	↑link
5	TVET Actors	10.5281/zenodo.3843350	↑link
6	Themes, Perspectives and Current Debates in TVET rResearch	10.5281/zenodo.3843352	↑link
7	Systematic rReview of TVET rResearch	10.5281/zenodo.3843354	↑link
8	Models for dDesigning, dDeveloping and dDelivering TVET	10.5281/zenodo.3843356	↑link
9	iInclusion-related Challenges and Policies	10.5281/zenodo.3843358	↑link
10	State aAuthorities for TVET mManagement	10.5281/zenodo.3843360	↑link
11	Non-state TVET pProviders	10.5281/zenodo.3843362	↑link
12	National sStandards and rRegulations	10.5281/zenodo.3843364	↑link
13	Challenges to pPolicy iImplementation	10.5281/zenodo.3843366	↑link
14	Insights Regarding Institutional Frameworks and Research Capacity	10.5281/zenodo.3843368	↑link
15	Research nNetworks and cCapacity bBuilding	10.5281/zenodo.3843370	↑link
16	Perspectives on Future TVET Research	10.5281/zenodo.3843372	↑link

5.3. Additional resources

5.3.1. Data Log

Haßler, B., et al. (2020). *Data Log—Technical and Vocational Education and Training in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review of the Research Landscape*. VET Repository, Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung, Bonn, Germany. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3976866](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3976866). Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/DYNH5EWU>. ([↑record](#))

5.3.2. Keywording sheet

Björn Haßler. (2019). *Keyword inventory for: Berufsbildung in Sub-Sahara Afrika - Eine systematische Aufarbeitung des Forschungsstandes* (10.5281/zenodo.3595604). Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3595604](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595604). Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/BIKE35W3>. ([↑record](#))

5.3.3. Presentation 1 (2019)

Kigwilu Changilwa, P., Haßler, B., Marsden, M., Watson, J., Schaffer, J., Kagambega, A., Iseje, F., Maseko, V., Orji, C. T., Deodonne, K., Amina, I., Ewnetu, T., & Ezekoye, B. (2019, June). *Technical and vocational education and training in sub-Saharan Africa: A comprehensive review of the current state of the research*. AfriTVET International Conference, RVTTI, Kenya, June 2019. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3976864](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3976864). Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/JCQQCLAY>. (↑record)

5.3.4. Presentation 2 (2019)

Haßler, B., Marsden, M., Iseje, F., Deodonne, K., Changilwa, P., & Maseko, V. (2019, September 3). *Technical and vocational education and training in sub-Saharan Africa: A comprehensive review of the current state of the research*. VETNET @ ECER. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3385078](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3385078). Available from <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/3V5L7IWH>. (↑record)

5.4. Zotero libraries

As noted in Chapter 3, all bibliographic data used in this report is available in our evidence library¹ as well as in a dedicated Zotero library². In the digital version of this report, all references are clickable and lead to the corresponding entry in the Open Development & Education evidence library; in other words, for all publications discussed in this report, basic bibliographic information is available for review. No username or password is required to look up the publications and their details. Some extended functionalities are available after login; users are invited to register here³ to join the shared library.

5.5. Appendix bibliography

This bibliography can be accessed from the [↑entry for this document in our evidence library](#). As this chapter is bibliographic in nature, the bibliography is not repeated here.

1 ↑Open Development & Education, Evidence Library, available at <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/>

2 ↑Open Development & Education, Zotero Library, available at https://www.zotero.org/groups/2317526/oden_tvetr-ssa/library

3 ↑Open Development & Education, TVET Zotero Library Registration, available at https://www.zotero.org/groups/2317526/oden_tvetr-ssa?

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- work place by priyanka from Noun Project, <https://thenounproject.com/search?q=1894975&i=1894975>.

